

ELECTRICAL MEASURING INSTRUMENTS

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As we all know, in physics classes we are taught different types of electrical measuring instruments and the principle of operation. We know that the role of these devices in saving electricity is very important.

Electrical units of the measurement system are used to express standard electrical units in order to make people easy to understand. There are two unit systems that can be used; they are the international system (SI) and the imperial system (Britain) that applies in Europe . Since the 1960s the international unit system (SI) has been used as an international standard unit . The SI unit contains a list of quantities and symbols that are used in the fields of electricity and magnetism worldwide

We're going to get acquainted with devices that work on these units. It is considered important for us to know these devices and use them in our daily lives.

TABLE I
ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS AND UNIT SI

Parameters	Unit	Symbol
Current (I)	Amper	A
Voltage (V)	Volt	V
Electromotive force (ε)	Volt	V
Resistance (R)	ohm	Ω
Electric Charge (Q)	coulomb	C
Capacitance (C)	Farad	F
Electric Power (P)	Watt	W
Frequency (F)	Hertz	Hz
Conductance (G)	Siemens	S
Magnetic Flux (Φ)	Weber	Wb
Flux Density (B)	Tesla	T
Inductance (L)	Henry	H
Energy (E)	Joule	J

Basically there are five types of measuring instruments and they are Ohm meter , Volt meter, amper meter, watt meter, tacho meter. Here we are interested in electrical measuring instruments so we will discuss about them in detail. Electrical instruments use mechanical system for the measurement of various electrical quantities but as we know that the all mechanical system has some inertia therefore electrical instruments have a limited time response .Now there are various ways of classifying the instruments . On broads Electricity is a flow that contains an electric charge and is related to physical phenomena. Until now, electricity had various purpose in supporting daily activities. In using electricity for your daily life, you need a device to measure electric voltage.

Well, here are some of the types of electric tools and their functions:

1. Ohm Meter

Ohm meter is a device that functions to measure the amount of electricity from a switch. According to ohm’s law, the circuit of electric current is directly proportional to the voltage. This device focuses more on resistance only.

Ohm meters are divided into two, one of them is analog ohm meters. It is a simpler device because it measures with a needle, so you have to be more precise in seeing where the number is located.

Digital ohm meter is an ohm meter that provides more accurate and detailed results. The disadvantage of this digital ohm meter is that it is difficult to monitor when the voltage fluctuates. This ohm meter also has the function of knowing the damage to an electrical circuit, so it can help your work faster.

2. Volt Meter

The next measuring instrument is a volt meter; this device has a function to measure the amount of voltage of an electric current flowing per second. This volt meter can measure the electric voltage within a predetermined maximum limit. If the voltage exceeds the limit it will cause damage to the device.

Volt meters also consist of two types, they are analog volt meters and digital volt meters. Analog volt meter works by using a needle, while digital volt meter can show you the number in detail.

3. Ampere Meter

The fourth type of electric measuring instrument is the ampere meter. This tool serves to measure the electric voltage current in a closed circuit. You only need to attach this ampere meter to the circuit of electric current you want to measure.

Voltmeters and Ammeters

Whereas voltmeters measure voltage, ammeters measure current. Some of the meters in automobile dashboards, digital cameras, cell phones, and tuner-amplifiers are actually voltmeters or ammeters (Figure 6.4.1). The internal construction of the simplest of these meters and how they are connected to the system they monitor give further insight into applications of series and parallel connections

Figure 6.4.2 (a) When an ammeter is used to measure the current through two resistors connected in series to a battery, a single ammeter is placed in series with the two resistors because the current is the same through the two resistors in series. (b) When two resistors are connected in parallel with a battery, three meters, or three separate ammeter readings, are necessary to measure the current from the battery and through each resistor. The ammeter is connected in series with the component in question.

Ammeters need to have a very low resistance, a fraction of a milliohm. If the resistance is not negligible, placing the ammeter in the circuit would change the equivalent resistance of the circuit and modify the current that is being measured. Since the current in the circuit travels through the meter, ammeters normally contain a fuse to protect the meter from damage from currents which are too high.

4. Watt Meter

The watt meter has a function to measure direct current power. This electric measuring device is a combination of an ampere meter and a volt meter. Besides being able to measure direct current power, the watt meter can also measure the power of a single phase alternating current and measure the power of a three-phase Measuring Voltage with a Voltmeter

A voltmeter is connected in parallel with whatever device it is measuring. A parallel connection is used because objects in parallel experience the same potential difference. (See Figure 6.4.3, where the voltmeter is represented by the symbol V.) alternating current.

Since voltmeters are connected in parallel, the voltmeter must have a very large resistance. Digital voltmeters convert the analog voltage into a digital value to display on a digital readout

5. Tacho Meter

The next type of electric measuring instrument is the tacho meter. This device has a function to measure the engine rotation of vehicles, such as cars and motorbikes. This device has a screen where it displays the speed of the vehicle. In addition, the taco meter is also used to measure the safe point that shows the vehicle rotation speed.

Conculision : When measuring instruments are used by consumers, standardization should meet the label to ensure the quality and safety of the equipment. Each country has different rules or policies for branding products sold in the country. In general, if a measuring instrument does not meet the standard requirements of a country, then the instrument cannot be sold in that country. You don't need strong knowledge and security to know these devices, because you'll also encounter devices that you see in cars a day in your daily lives. The most important thing is to choose and use the quality of these devices. I'm glad I've been provided with any important information.

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